

Effect of School-Stakeholders Partnership Approach and Participation Rate of Indigenous People Learners

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Abstract. This study sought to determine the effect of stake-holders partnership on the participation rate of the IP learners. Eventually, it also sought to determine the magnitude of effect of the action initiated by the researcher on the reading schema of the research subjects. This study will be conducted in Cluster XII Secondary and Integrated Schools. The subjects of this study would be the 45 IP Learners – 22 constitutes the controlled group and 23 composed the experimental group. The composition of these two groups were IP learners whose houses were distant from school. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study. This study would utilize the the researcher anecdotal record where the attendance of the IP learners was recorded and kept. The researcher would record the attendance of the IP learners from controlled and experimental groups. The experiment would had a time frame of one month to determine if there was increase or status quo in the attendance of the research subjects in the experimental group by the time her initiated program was implemented. This study revealed that the school-stakeholders partnership had increased the attendance of the IP learners. It also revealed that there was magnitude of difference between the pre-implementation and post implementation attendance of the IP learners of the controlled and experimental groups.

KEY WORDS

1. stakeholders' partnership 2. participation rate 3. IP learners

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1. Introduction

In many cases around the world, education available to indigenous peoples was not only inappropriate, it also threatened their very existence. Education policies and systems had often been used as a means to systemically discriminate against indigenous peoples, assimilate them (and at times “civilize” them) into the broader society, and thus destroy their culture, languages, identity and rights, and displace them of their lands, territories and natural resources. There were education systems, policies and curricula which were rarely developed with indigenous peoples’ participation or consent, and as a result have mostly failed indigenous children and stripped them from vital life opportunities and cultural security (Howard, 2020). Given the importance of lands and natural resources to the livelihoods, culture and well-being of indigenous peoples, their traditional knowledge about their lands was also interconnected to education, where elders passed down knowledge, values and their histories to new

generations. In every way then, the right to education was connected to all other human rights of indigenous peoples, including land rights (Maybury-Lewis, 2022). Indigenous Filipinos were among the many indigenous peoples (IP) who have experienced devastating destruction of their homes, imposition of settlers in their ancestral domains, and retreats to areas far from basic social services. Approximately 110 ethnic tribes live in the Philippines, most of whom fight for their way of life for themselves and future generations as they struggle to keep their lands. (Ricarte, 2021). With regard to education, the IP were among those with the lowest literacy rates. It was a challenge to serve their needs in remote areas, and standard education programs failed to take into account their cultures, languages, and current realities. In an attempt to respond to these challenges, the Department of Education in the Philippines had recently adopted the Indigenous Peoples Curriculum Education Framework (DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2015) as a guide for IP educators in developing “culturally appropriate and responsive” curricula, lesson plans, instructional materials, and teaching methods. IP education was unique in that it often takes approaches different from those used in traditional instruction. The importance of highlighting indigenous knowledge, skills, practices, and values was acknowledged and incorporated. To effectively teach IP learners, it was crucial to understand the world as perceived through their eyes. Only when connections were made between new information being presented and a child’s known way of life can learning be relevant and have life-long value. Even as changes through education were intended for the good of their community, all efforts must respect their identity as Ips (Merlan, 2020). Openness was key in nurturing a dynamic where teachers and students learn from each other. Respect for the dignity of each community member was manifested in respect for their entire culture. Education programs for

such communities bear good fruit when they were facilitated rather than forced. All key players need to recognize the abundance in both human and natural resources in the community as education harnesses the many strengths that had been theirs all along (Pratt, 2021). For the past decade the 21st Century Community Learning Centers initiative had asked schools to work in partnership with community- and faith-based organizations to support children’s learning during the hours after school and during the summertime. Consequently, there had been tremendous growth across the nation in intentional efforts to forge meaningful partnerships between schools and afterschool and summer programs. When schools and community organizations worked together to support learning, everyone benefited. Partnerships could serve to strengthen, support, and even transform individual partners, resulting in improved program quality, more efficient use of resources, and better alignment of goals and curricula (Brandenberger, 2020). To support student learning directly, partnerships could have additional benefits to students and their families. They could provide continuity of services across the day and year, easing school transitions and promoting improved attendance in after school programs; facilitating access to a range of learning opportunities and developmental supports, providing opportunities for students and teachers alike to experiment with new approaches to teaching and learning; facilitating information sharing about specific students to best support individual learning; and providing family members with alternative entry points into the school day to support their student’s learning (Merlan, 2020). Learning partnerships of school and barangay could also greatly benefit schools. They could complement the academic curriculum with a wider range of services and activities, particularly enrichment and arts activities that may not be available during the school day; supported transitions across the school years,

O₁ x O₂

O₃ x O₄

Where:

O₁ - Pretest of the experimental group

O₂ - Posttest of the experimental group

O₃ - Pretest of the controlled group

O₄ - Posttest of the controlled group

--- - Non-random assignment of subjects

X - Treatment applied in the experimental group

particularly the critical middle to high school transition, which research indicates was a key predictor of high school graduation; reinforced concepts taught in school without replicating the school day, often exposing classroom teachers working in the after school program to new pedagogies; improved school culture and community image through exhibitions and performances that help “shine the light” on students whose talents may not be apparent in the classroom; and gained access to mentors, afterschool staff, and other resources to support in-school learning and improved the teaching and learning in the classroom itself (Pratt, 2021). Learning partnerships with schools could strengthen and support community partners. They could help gain access to and recruit groups of students most in need of support services; improved pro-

gram quality and staff engagement, particularly when there was crossover between school and community organization staff; fostered better alignment of programming to support a shared vision for learning, one which aligns curriculum to support state and local standards; and maximized resource use such as facilities, staff, data, and curriculum (Johansen, 2021). In the Division of Davao City, particularly in Malabog District, there were schools which had IP learners. The prevalent problem was that their houses are in distant places that they were late in coming to school and eventually many of them quit schooling in the middle of the school year. The researcher being one of the teachers who had IP learners in the class felt this pressing problem. Hence, this research study.

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study made use of the quasi-experimental research design which was a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design was a good design when the researcher had ac-

cess to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study were intact groups of learners. This design was represented as follows:

2.2. Research Respondents—This study will be conducted in Cluster XII Secondary and

Integrated Schools. The subjects of this study would be the 45 IP Learners – 22 constitutes the

Distribution of Respondents

	Subjects	No. of Pupils
1	Section A	22
2	Section B	23
	Total	45

controlled group and 23 composed the experimental group. The composition of these two groups were IP learners whose houses were distant from school. This study made use of the

non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study would utilize the the researcher anecdotal record where the attendance of the IP learners was recorded and kept. The researcher would record the attendance of the IP learners from controlled and experimental groups. The experi-

ment would have a time frame of one month to determine if there was increase or status quo in the attendance of the research subjects in the experimental group by the time her initiated program is implemented.

To determine participation rate of the IP learners, the following continuum will be used.

Scale Levels for Attendance or Participation Rate of IP Learners

Range of Increase	Level	Criteria
<i>Adjustable Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
100% and above	Very High	When the attendance or participation rate of the IP learners increases by 100% or more compared to last month
80% - 99%	High	When the attendance or participation rate of the IP learners increases by 80% to 99% compared to last month
60% - 79%	Moderate	When the attendance or participation rate of the IP learners increases by 60% to 79% compared to last month
40% - 59%	Low	When the attendance or participation rate of the IP learners increases by 40% to 59% compared to last month
20% - 39%	Very Low	When the attendance or participation rate of the IP learners increases by 20% to 39% compared to last month

Note: IP = Indigenous Peoples.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—

At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher would draft a letter seeking for permission that this research study be conducted were sent to the Dr. Reynante A. Solitario, the Schools Division Superintendent in the division of Davao City and to the School Principal of the concerned school in Cluster. While letters sought for permission were delivered to the DepED Schools Division Superintendent and principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and had it validated by the ex-

perts preferably the experts of the study. After permission had been granted that this study be conducted in the respondent-school in Cluster XII Secondary and Integrated Schools and after the research questionnaire had been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher would commence her experiment. Results of the study would be submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher would made analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools would be used in the analysis and interpretation the responses in this study. Mean would be used to describe the level of participation rate of the IP learners. t-test for uncor-

related samples would be used to test the significance of difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores in the experimental and n groups. Eta square would be used to measure the magnitude of effect of stakeholders partnership on the participation rate of IP learners.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented the discussion of the problems in this study. They were discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

Pre-implementation Attendance of the IP Learners Table 1 disclosed the pre-implementation attendance of the IP learners.

The controlled group got the mean of 3.45 or Moderate while the experimental group got the mean of 3.42 or Moderate.

Table 1. Pre-implementation Attendance of IP Learners

Group	n	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
<i>Controlled Group</i>	22	3.45	Moderate
<i>Experimental Group</i>	23	3.42	Moderate

Note: IP = Indigenous Peoples.

It could be gleaned from the table that during pre-implementation attendance of the experimental group had a lower mean rating compared to the controlled group although both belongs Moderate level. This finding was congruent to the idea of Rabren (2019) who said

that indigenous children were more likely to arrive at school hungry, ill and tired; they were often bullied, and the used of corporal punishment was still widespread. Ethnic and cultural discrimination at schools were major obstacles to equal access to education, causing

poor performance and higher dropout rates. Indigenous girls, in particular, experienced difficult problems related to unfriendly school environments, gender discrimination, school-based violence and sometimes sexual abused, all of which contributed to high dropout rates. Post-implementation attendance of the IP learners Shown in table 2 were the data on the post-implementation attendance of the IP learners.

The controlled group got the mean of 4.20 or High while the experimental group gained the mean of 4.35 or Very High. It could be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group had a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 0.93 from a mean rating of 3.42 to 4.35. This meant that experimental group had a far better performance than the controlled group.

Table 2. Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
<i>Controlled Group</i>	22	4.20	High
<i>Experimental Group</i>	23	4.35	Very High

Note: Descriptive Equivalent rating scale: High = 80-89%, Very High = 90-100%.

This finding was congruent to the idea of Sheldon (2018) who expressed that Indigenous students frequently find that the education they were offered by the state promotes individualism and a competitive atmosphere, rather than communal ways of life and cooperation. They were not taught relevant survival and work skills suitable for indigenous economies, and they often returned to their communities with a formal education that was irrelevant or unsuitable for their needs. They were forced to seek employment in the national economy, leading to a vicious cycle of social fragmentation, brain drain and a lack of development, especially because the jobs and salaries available to them often would not match their educational achievements. The devastation of colonialism had shaped our shared, but different, experiences as Indigenous people. From our natural environment and relational structures that enabled collective well-being to our cultural knowledge systems to our languages, and ceremonial practices, colonial-

ism had disrupted and fragmented our ways of being. Education was both a target and tool of colonialism, destroying and diminishing the validity and legitimacy of Indigenous education, while simultaneously replacing and reshaping it with an ‘education’ complicit with the colonial endeavor. Schooling as a formalized colonial structure served as a vehicle for wider imperialist ideological objectives (OSEP, 2020). Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score.

Table 3 showed the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.32 with a p-value of .0211 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which meant that there was a significant difference between the pre-implementation attendance and post-implementation attendance of the IP learners. This implied that the stakeholders’ partnership had contributed to the increase of attendance of the IP learners in school.

This finding was in line with the statement of OSEP (2020) which stated that openness was

key in nurturing a dynamic where teachers and students learn from each other. Respect for the

Table 3. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-implementation and Post-implementation attendance of the IP learners

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-implementation and Post-implementation	45	-5.42	.0321	Significant

Note: The degrees of freedom (df) represent the sample size minus 1.

dignity of each community member was manifested in respect for their entire culture. Education programs for such communities bore good fruit when they were facilitated rather than forced. All key players need to recognized the abundance in both human and natural resources in the community as education harnesses the many strengths that had been theirs all along (U.S. Department of Education, Office of Special Education Programs [OSEP], 2020). Only when connections were made between new information being presented and a child’s known way of life can learning be relevant and have life-long value. Even as changes through education were intended for the good of their community, all efforts must be respected to their identity as Ips. Test on the Magnitude of Difference be-

tween the Pretest and Post test Scores of the IP learners

Table 4 highlighted the test of Mom’s reading class on the reading proficiency of grade five pupils. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.315 which signified a large effect. This implies that school with IP learners should intensified their partnership with the stakeholders in order come up with a program that would eventually attract learners to go to school every day. In the case of the IP learners who were marginalized in society, they also suffered from poverty that hinders them from going to school. Therefore, schools must have initiative to increase their attendance in school and one of the best initiatives was to tie up with stakeholders to develop a program that addresses this social problem.

Table 4. Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pre- and Post-test Scores of the Grade 5 Students

N	t-value	Eta2	Descriptive Value	Decision
42	-4.22	0.315	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

Note: N represents the sample size.

This finding was in line with the idea of Coleman (2021) who cited that IPed Program had strengthened the enabling conditions for culture-based education while promoting the value of indigenous identity, knowledge, competencies, and other aspects of their cultural heritage (Coleman, 2021). He further said that Indigenous peoples do not came only with prob-

lems that need solving – we came with our own answers and ask your assistance in ensuring these solutions were systematically and fully implemented. Quality in education was not an absolute and static concept, because education relates to the culture and community it was supposed to serve.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displayed the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made. This study sought to determine the effect of School-stakeholders partnership on the participation rate of IP learners.

4.1. Findings—This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which was a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. In this case, it was the pre-implementation and post-implementation attendance of the IP learners that were considered primary data. Non-equivalent design was a good design when the researcher had access to one group for experimentation (Vockel, 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study were intact group of learners. This study will be conducted in Cluster XII Secondary and Integrated Schools. The subjects of this study would be the 45 IP Learners – 22 constitutes the controlled group and 23 composes the experimental group. The composition of these two groups were IP learners whose houses were distant from school. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the school-stakeholders partnership had increased the attendance of the IP learners. It also revealed that there was magnitude of difference between the pre-implementation and post implementation attendance of the IP learners of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions were drawn: The pre-implementation attendance of the IP learners in both the controlled and experimental groups was at Moderate level. The post-implementation attendance of the controlled group was high while the post-attendance attendance of the of the experimental group was at Moderate level.

4.3. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations were offered: It was recommended that DepEd officials would strengthen the implementation of policies on partnerships where school had to forged contract of Memorandum of Understanding with stakeholders in order to come up with programs that would help achieve the vision of the department and would also help generate higher academic outcome. The school heads should expand its partnership to other stakeholders of the school in order to come up with various programs which primary purpose was to entice learners to go to school regularly and eventually achieve a higher academic outcomes. For future researchers, it was strongly recommended that a relative study on school-stakeholders partnership in relation to other indicators in school, may it be academic or in school operations would be conducted.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

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